

Robotic Manipulators for Harsh Environments Based on Rolling Diaphragm Hydrostatic Transmissions

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Abstract—Rolling Diaphragm Hydrostatic Transmissions (RDHTs) represent an innovative approach to robotic actuation, offering significant benefits such as remote placement of actuators and electronics, enhanced low-friction operation, high transparency, and precise force controllability. RDHTs have been successfully implemented in various applications, including collaborative robots, medical systems, and untethered platforms like legged and wearable robots. Moreover, RDHT technology presents a promising opportunity for the development of a new class of robotic systems capable of operating reliably and accurately in harsh environments, including high-temperature, underwater, and radioactive scenarios.

In this paper, we review and discuss the potential of RDHTs for enabling robust robotics in extreme environments and present preliminary yet highly promising results from the development of a novel robotic arm designed specifically for these challenging applications.

Index Terms—Rolling Diaphragm Transmission, Harsh Environment Robotics

I. INTRODUCTION

Robots were originally conceived to relieve humans from performing hard, repetitive, laborious, and tiring tasks. Over the last half-century, they have successfully achieved this in many applications. In addition, robots have been effectively employed to cooperate with humans, enhancing their capabilities in precision tasks or in activities requiring high force or endurance [1].

However, these robots typically operate in controlled industrial settings or human-designed scenarios with stable environmental conditions such as temperature, pressure, and humidity. A significant challenge that remains is designing robots capable of operating in extremely harsh environments, such as underwater, high-temperature, or radioactive settings, where their deployment is still limited. In these scenarios, humans continue to be employed despite the substantial associated risks.

In this contribution, we briefly review the limitations of conventional robots in three different challenging environments—high temperature, underwater, and radioactive—and illustrate how RDHTs could be an enabling technology to

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Fig. 1. Scheme of a robotic system actuated through RDHT (top) and scheme of the working principle of the RDHT.

develop robots that operate in these peculiar conditions. Additionally, we present preliminary but promising results on the characterization of such technology in the context of underwater and radioactive environments, demonstrating its actual potential in these application fields.

II. RDHTs FOR CHALLENGING ENVIRONMENTS

Rolling Diaphragm Hydrostatic Transmissions (RDHTs) have emerged as a compelling solution for actuator remotization, offering a unique combination of transparency, low friction, and high torque density [2]–[4]. RDHTs have been applied in a variety of domains, including telepresence systems [5], MRI-compatible devices [6], upper- and lower-limb exoskeletons [7], and wearable supernumerary limbs [8]. They embody the “gentle-yet-powerful” paradigm by combining the high specific torque and stiffness of hydraulic systems with the ease of control associated with electric actuators.

Additionally, there are a few less obvious features that make this technology suitable for harsh environments characterized by high temperature, high-pressure liquids, and nuclear radiation. In particular, *high-temperature environments* pose significant challenges to robotic systems, primarily due to the risk of overheating and the degradation of materials and

components. Standard electronic parts and actuators, especially electric motors, struggle to dissipate heat efficiently at elevated temperatures, leading to potential overheating, insulation breakdown, and reduced efficiency. This issue is compounded by the fact that conventional cooling techniques, such as fans or liquid cooling, become less effective or infeasible in such environments. For electrical components and motors, specialized high-temperature insulation materials and forced convection cooling systems are often implemented at the cost of increased complexity and specialization of the robotic design [9].

In these environments, RDHTs offer a simple but effective solution for remote actuation, where, for example, the motors are located outside the high-temperature zone or in a fixed box that can be easily cooled. In addition, RDHTs are sufficiently tolerant to high temperatures (up to 100–150°C and potentially even higher) and to deformations caused by temperature variations since the mechanical accuracy required for their operation is relatively coarse. *Space applications*, in which heat dissipation is of utmost importance due to operation in high vacuum, are a territory where RDHTs could represent a breakthrough. Similarly, *radiation environments* where high levels of nuclear radiation are present pose several challenges for robotic systems due to the low resistance of sensing and electronic components [10]. Radiation-resistant robots (Rad-hard) are difficult to design, as shielding made of heavy lead or steel plates has to be integrated onboard the manipulator. In this context, RDHT-based robots offer an excellent solution due to two key advantages: the intrinsic high radiation resistance of the passive robotic manipulator and the remote actuation, which allows for easy shielding of the actuators, sensors, and control electronics.

Regarding *underwater environments*, unlike the previously mentioned challenging environments, robots are already widely employed at depth. However, their performance is quite limited due to the inherent low quality of control, which can be mainly attributed to the high friction introduced by the sliding seals of the robot joints. This issue is especially relevant for robots that operate at great depths, where the preload of seals must overcome significant external pressures. In this case, RDHTs offer a simple solution to achieve perfect static sealing of the actuators and electronics while guaranteeing frictionless operation at the joints of the robotic manipulator.

However, we also have to underline the challenges related to the design of a passive manipulator that is remotely actuated through RDHTs. A first limitation is identified in the solutions for reaching the joints of the robot using flexible piping that must be compliant with the mobility of the manipulator. Second, the remotization comes with a cost on the bandwidth of the transmission [2] due to the intrinsic flexibility introduced between actuators and robot links. Lastly, although the use of rolling diaphragms is widespread in industry, the reliability of these components when employed as drivers for robotic systems is still untested.

III. PRELIMINARY ACHIEVEMENTS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In line with these promising directions, our group has made significant progress towards the design and implementation of a novel manipulator that could potentially be employed in several of the aforementioned environments. Preliminary tests have shown encouraging results in terms of reliability and performance under harsh conditions. Specifically, a 4-DoF manipulator actuated through an RDHT system has been successfully developed and integrated, demonstrating the feasibility of implementing a multi-DoF robotic system using this technology (see demo video). Additionally, a prototype of a robotic joint is currently undergoing radiation testing at the Calliope gamma irradiation plant at ENEA (Italy) [11], having reached a cumulative radiation dose exceeding 1.4 MGy. Future work will focus on optimizing the design for specific applications, conducting extensive durability testing, and exploring advanced materials to extend operational limits.

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